

Machining of FRP Composites by Abrasive jet machining and optimization using Taguchi

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Abstract : Abrasive Jet Machining is a Unconventional machining process in which the metal is removed from brittle and hard material in the form of micro-chips. With increase in need of materials like ceramics, composites, in manufacturing of various Mechanical & Electronic components, AJM has become a useful technique for micro machining. The present study highlights the influence of different parameters like Pressure, SOD, Time, Abrasive grain size, nozzle diameter on the Metal removal of FRP (Fiber Reinforced Polymer) composite by Abrasive jet machining. The results of the Experiments conducted were Analyzed and optimized with TAGUCHI method of Optimization and ANOVA for Optimal Value.

Keywords : ANOVA, FRP Composite, Time, Grain size, AJC, Pressure, SOD

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